

TECHNICAL NOTE

Game title: TO URGE: Deliberative democracy now!

Didactic-pedagogical content: EU-CIEMBLy – UC team

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The Game “TO URGE: Deliberative democracy now!” was developed in the framework of a European Union-funded Project, **EU-CIEMBLy, Creating an Inclusive European Citizens’ Assembly**. The game is based on a glossary (<https://www.eu-ciembly.eu/en/glossary>) aimed at citizens who are interested in becoming more actively involved in decision-making processes within the scope of different public policies or who want to better understand what role they can play in transformative processes, in which they can participate as actors and not just as spectators, particularly through citizens' assemblies.

The glossary of **Deliberative democracy** includes more than a hundred of concepts explained in clear language (verbally and with images) that can be used not only in the context of organising and participating in these assemblies, but also as part of pedagogical training and empowerment activities with educational, associative, inclusive, reintegration contexts, or simply playful.

From one hundred and sixty-two concepts, 28 were selected to make the game **“To URGE: deliberative democracy now”**. The **aim** of the game is to help young people learn about democratic concepts through simple definitions and visual language.

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TO URGE:

DELIBERATIVE

DEMOCRACY

NOW

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▶ Game narrative

Extraterrestrial visitors have just arrived in the city from a planet – let's call it Mars – where the inhabitants do not know what democracy is. It is a technologically highly developed planet that can travel interstellar distances, but there are no elections or democratic institutions, there is no respect for human rights, there are no inclusive practices, direct or indirect discrimination is constant, and justice and equity are unknown concepts. What is most worrying is that this democratic ignorance is transmitted by a bacterium (*anti-democratis bacter*) that can only be combated through the rapid administration of concentrated doses of knowledge.

The mission of the participants is to bring concentrated knowledge to the Martians using clear language and simple images to break down linguistic obstacles.

► Game concepts

Concepts related to deliberative democracy, organised by theme

1. Concepts about citizenship

Citizenship
Civil society organizations
European citizen
Non-governmental
organisation

2. Concepts about participation

Access to information
Democratic participation
Egalitarian democracy
Public participation

3. Concepts about Democracy

Deliberative democracy
Democratic deficit
Participatory democracy
Representative democracy

4. Concepts about democratic institutions

European Parliament
Elections
Referendum
Political party

4. Concepts about negative effects that should be prevented

Direct discrimination
Indirect discrimination
Discrimination by
association
Discrimination by
assumption
Bias
Stereotype
Algorithmic discrimination
Multiple discrimination

5. Concepts about positive effects that should be promoted

Distributive justice
Equity
Fairness
Formal equality

Concepts related to deliberative democracy, organised in alphabetical order

Access to information
Algorithmic discrimination
Bias
Citizenship
Civil society organisations
Deliberative democracy
Democratic deficit
Democratic participation
Direct discrimination
Discrimination by association
Discrimination by assumption
Distributive justice
Egalitarian democracy
Elections
Equity
European citizen
European Parliament
Fairness
Formal equality
Indirect discrimination
Multiple discrimination
Non-governmental organisation
Participatory democracy
Political party
Public participation
Referendum
Representative democracy
Stereotype

► Game material

7 A2 size cardboard posters, with 4 concepts each

 Self-adhesive velcro tape to stick next to the concepts.

28 cards (1/2 A4 cut into 2/3 + 1/3) with 1 concept definition on each, printed on the front and with velcro on the back

28 Cards with the icons on the front, and the definition in clear language (shorter) and velcro on the back

Card definition

card icon (front)

card icon (back)

The plain language version is printed on the back of the icon.

Other materials:

Seven antennae to identify Martians.

A bell to indicate the start of the game.

A stopwatch to measure game times.

▶ Objective of the game

Bring together concepts with definitions in the shortest possible time.

The team of 5 people (4 therapists + 1 Martian) who managed to correctly combine the 4 concepts the quickest wins.

The game supports multiple rounds.

▶ Players

The game is aimed at secondary school students aged 14 and over. It can be played with any number of players, preferably multiples of 4. Students can take on the role of either Martians or therapists. The roles to be played are drawn by cutting out as many pieces of paper as players. Some of the papers have the word 'Martian' written and the rest say nothing (by default, they will be the therapists). The papers are folded in four and mixed up. Each student draws a piece of paper to indicate their role in the game.

For greater speed, the roles can be self-proposed by the students. The roles can also be assigned by the facilitator, reserving the role of Martian for those who are less able to move around. The role of therapist involves running from one place to another.

The concept posters are then raffled off by the Martians.

► Game organisation

28 players, 7 Martians and 21 therapists.

If there are more than 28, the rest will be therapists and will play in the second round, trying to associate the icons with the concepts.

24 players, 6 Martians and 18 therapists.

If there are 25 to 27 players, play as if there were 24 (6 Martians) and the rest will be therapists and will play in the second round, trying to associate the icons with the concepts.

20 players, 5 Martians and 15 therapists

If there are 21 to 23 players, play as if there were 20 (5 Martians) and the rest will be therapists and will play in the second round, trying to associate the icons with the concepts.

16 players, 4 Martians and 12 therapists.

If there are 13 to 15 players, play as if there were 12 (4 Martians) and the rest will be therapists and will play in the second round, trying to associate the icons with the concepts.

With fewer players the game is played with two rounds of concepts

12 players, 3 Martians with 2 concept posters each and 9 therapists. The therapists will successively collect the 12 concepts that are in play in the first round and the 12 concepts from the second round.

If there are 9 to 11 players, play as if there were 8 (2 Martians) and the rest will be therapists and will play in the second round, trying to associate the icons with the concepts.

8 players, 2 Martians with 3 concept posters each and 6 therapists with 3 definition cards each. The therapists will successively collect the 8 concepts that are in play in the first round, 8 more in the second round and 8 in the third round.

With fewer players, there are no Martians. The concept posters (as many as you want) are now stuck to a wall and the therapists must go and get the corresponding definition cards from the opposite side of the room, the same being done for the icons.

▶ Game layout

The room should be clear, allowing therapists to move quickly from one side to the other.

The Martians stand side by side, each holding a concept card, on one side of the room. On the opposite side of the room are the definition cards and icon cards, arranged randomly on tables.

▶ Game mechanics

A bell (on the mobile phone) signals the start of the game and the therapists all run simultaneously to get a definition card each. They then look for the Martian who holds the concept corresponding to their definition.

When a therapist considers that he has found the concept corresponding to his definition, he confirms whether the Martian also agrees that this is the correct definition of the concept.

The definition on the poster can only be pasted if both agree.

After associating the concepts, the therapists race to find the corresponding icon. The second round is to associate the icons with the definitions and respective concepts. After finding the right concept for their definition, the therapists race to find the corresponding icon. When they think they have found the right icon, they check the opinion of the Martian and, if there is agreement, they stick the icon on the poster next to the definition.

When the completion of a concept card has been completed, the Martian and the 4 therapists shout in unison: **Democracy!**

As each poster is completed, the facilitators time and record the completion time.

Once all the posters have been filled with the 4 definitions and icons, the facilitators check, with the help of the concept verification table, whether all the 'concept-definition-icon' associations are correct, starting with the fastest group. If they are, shout: '**Democracy won!**' If they are not, shout! '**correction**' pointing to the concept whose definition or icon is wrong. In

this case, therapists must check which is the correct definition or icon and switch between posters. Repeat until all posters are filled out correctly.

► Inter-school competition

All timed rounds are compared, and the school whose team has completed the card with the correct concepts, definitions and icons in the shortest time wins.

► Pedagogical development

The winning team reads each of their concepts and their definitions out loud. A survey is conducted (by raising hands) to count the number of players who did not know each of the 4 concepts.

If there is time, the reading aloud and the survey for all the concepts in play are repeated. If there is no time, the facilitators select the most complex concepts.

The most unknown concept wins.

In the inter-school tournament modality, lesser-known concepts are recorded in the concept verification table.

Students from different teams can be invited to do group work by inventing a story that illustrates the most unknown concept (or another concept in play that the facilitators consider to be important).

Students have 15/20 minutes to create a story with a surprising ending.

The stories are read aloud by the spokesperson of each group, with the winning group of the Game being the last one to read their story.

At the end, all students vote (in a secret ballot using slips of paper) to choose the best story.

If there is time, each team can campaign for their story, trying to persuade their colleagues to choose their story, using arguments related to what they have learned about participatory democracy. They have 10 minutes to come up with arguments that demonstrate that their story is better than the others. The spokesperson must present only the strong points of their story in a maximum of 2 minutes and may not belittle, ridicule or offend the stories of the other teams, under penalty of disqualification. They can, for example, argue that their group's story is the best because it is the most truthful, the most imaginative, the most detailed, the most current, the most original, the most impressive, the most detailed, the most factual, the most exciting, the most frightening, the most moving, the funniest, the most memorable, etc.

At the end, all students vote again, in a secret ballot (using pieces of paper) to choose the best story after the campaign.

Citizenship

Civil Society Organisations

European Citizen

Non-governmental Organisation

Distributive justice

Equity

Fairness

Formal equality

Access to information

Democratic participation

Egalitarian democracy

Public participation

Deliberative democracy

[]

[]

Participatory democracy

[]

[]

[]

[]

[]

[]

Democratic deficit

Representative democracy

European Parliament

Election

Referendum

Political party

Direct discrimination

Discrimination by association

Indirect discrimination

Discrimination by assumption

Bias

Stereotype

[Empty dashed box]

[Empty dashed box]

[Empty dashed box]

[Empty dashed box]

[Empty dashed box]

[Empty dashed box]

[Empty dashed box]

[Empty dashed box]

Algorithmic discrimination

Multiple discrimination

 A particular legal bond between a national of a state acquired by birth or naturalisation, that entails specific rights and responsibilities towards that state

Non-State, non-for-profit
and non-violent structures
through which people
organise the pursuit of shared
objectives and ideals

A legally recognised
national of a Member State of
the European Union

Non-profit organisation that operates independently of any government and is established to work toward public or social goals

 Fair allocation of resources, benefits, opportunities and burdens in a society among individuals and groups

Fair distribution of opportunities, resources, and support to overcome systemic barriers and ensure that everyone—regardless of their background, identity, or circumstances—can fully participate in society

 Impartial and just treatment or behaviour of all participants and perspectives, without discrimination, favouritism, or bias throughout the deliberative process

 Equal treatment for all members of society, regardless of their specific characteristics

 The right of everyone, in equal terms, to have access, on request, to official documents held by public authorities. The access to information can be limited in specific situations related, for instance, to national security or the right to privacy

Right to engage in the democratic life of the political community. Democratic participation processes give citizens and civil society the possibility to take part in decision-making, providing input for policy changes

Democratic system that presupposes that the protection of rights and freedoms of individuals is equal across all social groups; resources are distributed equally across all social groups; and groups and individuals have equal access to power

 Any process under which citizens and civil society influence or engage in the activities and decision-making processes of public authorities

Process of active engagement and direct deliberation by citizens amongs themselves or with the participation of other stakeholders on a substantive policy or legislative area

Situation whereby institutions and their decision-making processes may suffer from a lack of democracy and accountability. In the case of the European Union, it refers to a perceived lack of accessibility or lack of representation of the ordinary citizen with respect to the European Union institutions

Democratic model that places emphasis on engaging citizens through co-creation and deliberative practices to help shape laws and public policies, rather than merely voting for representatives who make those decisions on their behalf

 Political system of government based on elected representatives through regular elections. The elected representatives are accountable to the electorate for their actions

A European Union institution directly elected by European Union citizens, for a period of 5 years, with legislative powers and whose main role is to ensure the democratic legitimacy of European law

Formal process that consists of selecting a person or persons who will act as representatives of the electorate to hold political office

 Instrument of direct democracy by which a measure passed or proposed by a legislative body or by popular initiative is submitted to popular vote

 Association of like-minded
which pursues political
objectives and is recognised by
law

Unfair or disadvantaged treatment of a person or groups because of a specific characteristic such as race or ethnic origin, gender, disability, or age

 Discriminatory effect of a practice, procedure, rule or policy that seems to be fair but exacerbates existing inequalities when implemented

A type of direct discrimination that occurs when a person has a connection or a relationship with a person or group with a protected characteristic such as race, disability, or religion

 Treating a person unfairly based on the mistaken belief (conscious or unconscious) that they have a particular characteristic, such as a specific race, gender, sexual orientation, or disability, regardless of whether the assumption is true or not. Also known as “perceived” discrimination

 Subjective distortion which prevents one from an objective and impartial decision, deferring to a pre-existing prejudice or judgement and stopping one from correct assessment

 A preconceived and oversimplified assumption that generalizes and often exaggerates the perceived traits of a specific group

Systematic and repeatable biases in computer systems that result in unfair outcomes, often disadvantaging certain groups based on factors such as race, gender, or age

 Discrimination based on more than one perceived characteristic of a person, community or group

Any person who holds the nationality of a state

Structured
group whose
members work
for the common
good

Any national of a
European Union
Member State

Non-profit
organisation that
has public or
social goals

Sharing
resources,
opportunities
and burdens
fairly

Fair treatment
and equitable
conditions for
different persons
and social
groups

Treating
everyone with
justice, without
discrimination
in decision-
making

Everyone has
identical rights
and
responsibilities

The right of
everyone to have
access to official
documents held
by public
authorities

Right to engage in
the democratic
life of the political
community

Democratic
system that
ensures equal
opportunities to
all, with fair
access to
resources

Citizens and civil
society
participation in
the activities and
decision-making
processes of
public authorities

Process of direct
deliberation by
citizens on a
substantive policy
or legislative area

Situations when
institutions suffer
from a lack of
democracy and
accountability

Democratic model
that engages
citizens through
co-creation and
deliberative
practices

Political system of
government
based on elected
representatives

A European Union
law-making body
directly elected
by European
Union citizens

Process or act to
choose a person
or persons to
hold political
office

When a question
is decided by
putting it to a
direct public vote

Association of
like-minded
people which
aims to exercise
political power

Less favourable
treatment
because of race
or ethnic origin,
gender, disability,
age, etc.

A rule or policy
that looks fair in
theory but is
unfair to a certain
group in practice

Less favourable
treatment of a
person based on
the link to someone
with a certain trait
as race, disability,
or religion

Treating someone unfairly because others believe they have a certain characteristic, such as a specific race, gender, or disability

Supporting or
opposing
someone or
something in an
unfair way
because personal
opinions influence
a fair judgment

A preconceived
idea that
generalizes and
exaggerates the
traits of a group

Unfair decisions
made by
computer systems
that disadvantage
certain groups

Different forms of
discrimination at
the same time

Less favourable treatment because of race or ethnic origin, gender, disability, age, etc.										
INDIRECT DISCRIMINATION		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Time	
Discriminatory effect of a practice, procedure, rule or policy that seems to be fair but exacerbates existing inequalities when implemented										
A rule or policy that looks fair in theory but is unfair to a certain group in practice										
DISCRIMINATION BY ASSOCIATION										
A type of direct discrimination that occurs when a person has a connection or a relationship with a person or group with a protected characteristic such as race, disability, or religion										
Less favourable treatment of a person based on the link to someone with a certain trait as race, disability, or religion										
DISCRIMINATION BY ASSUMPTION										
Treating a person unfairly based on the mistaken belief (conscious or unconscious) that they have a particular characteristic, such as a specific race, gender, sexual orientation, or disability, regardless of whether the assumption is true or not. Also known as “perceived” discrimination										
Treating someone unfairly because others believe they have a certain characteristic, such as a specific race, gender, or disability										
BIAS										
Subjective distortion which prevents one from an objective and impartial decision, deferring to a pre-existing prejudice or judgement and stopping one from correct assessment										
Supporting or opposing someone or something in an unfair way because personal opinions influence a fair judgment										
STEREOTYPE										
A preconceived and oversimplified assumption that generalizes and often exaggerates the perceived traits of a specific group										
A preconceived idea that generalizes and exaggerates the traits of a group										
ALGORITHMIC DISCRIMINATION										
Systematic and repeatable biases in computer systems that result in unfair outcomes, often disadvantaging certain groups based on factors such as race, gender, or age										
Unfair decisions made by computer systems that disadvantage certain groups										

MULTIPLE DISCRIMINATION		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Time
Discrimination based on more than one perceived characteristic of a person, community or group									
Different forms of discrimination at the same time									

School establishment			
Winning team			
Correct concepts			
Time			
Total duration			
Date			
Facilitators			
Notes			